

MISSION

eMISSion-free HV and MV transmissiON switchgear for AC and DC
01.01.2024 – 31.12.2027

Call identifier: HORIZON-CL5-2023-D3-01-12

D2.1: WP2 Discharge models and swarm data v1 released

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Submission date: 20/12/2024

Dissemination level		
PU	Public	X
SEN	Sensitive, limited under the conditions of the Grant Agreement	

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101135484

Document history

Issue date	Version	Changes made / Reason for this issue
20/12/2024	1.0	Initial report released.

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This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101135484

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This report describes the deliverable *D2.1 – WP2 Discharge models and swarm data v1 released* from the EU MISSION project. As the deliverable D2.1 consists of open-source software releases, this report primarily includes a brief discussion of the background of the software and data sets that have been published. Instructions for how to access the various computer codes and data sets are available in this report.

1 INTRODUCTION

Work package 2 in the MISSION project is partitioned into three tasks:

- 1) Investigation of transport data in various gas mixtures.
- 2) Development of computational models, and their verification and validation.
- 3) Partial discharge (PD) detection.

These tasks are organized as follows:

Task 2.1: Swarm parameters in $N_2/O_2/CO_2$ mixtures (Lead: ETHZ).

Task 2.2: Computational model development, validation and implementation (Lead: SINTEF).

Task 2.3: Partial discharge detection in HV switchgear (Lead: SINTEF).

For more detailed information on the contents in these tasks we refer the reader to the MISSION project description. Deliverable 2.1 (D2.1) in the MISSION project consists of publication of transport data in gases from Task 2.1 and early versions of the computer models from Task 2.2. More specifically, the D2.1 description is as follows:

Software releases (open-source): swarm parameter data obtained in task 2.1 and first version of model from task 2.2 (Early versions of the models will be released as open-source software and updated throughout the project period). Swarm Parameters for $N_2/O_2/CO_2$ mixtures will be published on Ixcat.

The deliverable is due 12 months after project start, i.e., no later than December 2024.

This report is an introduction to the data set and software releases contained in the D2.1, and is organized into three parts:

- Status of the swarm parameters and evaluation (section 2).
- Status of the 1D model for breakdown prediction (section 3).
- Status of the 3D model for partial discharge and streamer simulations (section 4).

Together, these three parts represent a full description of D2.1, as described in the MISSION project proposal. Each part will separately discuss the background for the data/software, the current status of the software, as well as access instructions and licensing aspects (if relevant).

2 STATUS OF SWARM PARAMETER MEASUREMENTS AND EVALUATION

The aim of Task 2.1 is to perform measurements in a Pulsed Townsend Experiment [1] for the pure gases of N_2 , O_2 , CO_2 , as well as for their binary and ternary mixture. From the measurements, swarm parameters are derived and made publicly available to provide input to numerical models (e.g., Task 2.2), and with it to support the development of SF_6 -free gas-insulated switchgear (GIS). The measurements will not only provide results with an extended measurement range compared to the state-of-the-art, but also with improved accuracy and an uncertainty estimation, which has not been reported to date. In addition, the raw data and the analysis tool used for processing raw data are made publicly available. In this way, users know how to interpret these swarm parameters, and have the

possibility to re-assess the data with expanded theoretical models. A publication on the open-access evaluation tool is currently in preparation and thus not a part of this report. Described in the following subsections are a short description of the experimental setup, the theoretical model when for evaluating the measurements, and some example measurements.

2.1 Experimental Method

The pulsed Townsend (PT) setup consists of two Rogowski profile electrodes inside a stainless steel vacuum vessel. The vessel is located inside a temperature-controlled room maintained at 21 °C. The experimental control parameters are the applied voltage (U), the spacing between the electrodes (L), and the gas pressure (p). This allows for varying the distance between the electrodes while keeping the electric field E to gas number density (N) ratio fixed (i.e., fixed E/N). The vessel temperature is monitored using two silicon temperature sensors (LMT70A) mounted on the outer surface of the vessel, see Figure 1. Electrons are generated inside the vessel by bombarding a photocathode with a 1.5 ns full width at half maximum (FWHM) duration UV laser pulse with a wavelength of 266 nm. The bandwidth of the system is estimated to be 36 MHz. The photocathode is a quartz crystal coated with a double-layer of magnesium (15-30 nm) and palladium (5-8 nm) mounted at the center of the cathode. Swarm parameters are obtained by the measurement and subsequent analysis of the displacement current of electrons and ions in different gas mixtures over a range of E/N -values. At each E/N , measurements for at least three different L values are carried out [2].

Figure 1: Schematic of the pulsed Townsend setup used here. Copied from [2].

2.2 Evaluation method

The considered Pulsed Townsend experimental setup can be described in a simplified way by employing a fluid modelling approach. Hereby, the behavior of an electron swarm within the electrode configuration can analytically be described with closed form solutions in terms of an externally measurable displacement current $I_{ext}(t)$. By measuring this current in the experimental setup and comparing it with an analytical expression, it is possible to extract relevant electron transport

coefficients such as the drift velocity W , the longitudinal diffusion coefficient D_L , and the effective ionization coefficient α_{net} .

Currently, we use the following analytical curve fitting expression below, taken from [1] that is based on a Pulsed Townsend experiment model, where the initial electron distribution is assumed as a Dirac pulse at $z = 0$ (initial condition at $t = 0$) and a half-infinite spatial domain with the cathode at $z = -\infty$, and an absorbing anode at $z = L$ is considered (boundary conditions).

$$I_{\text{ext}}(t) = \frac{n_0 \cdot q \cdot W}{2 \cdot L} \exp(R_{\text{net}} \cdot (t - t_0)) \left\{ \left[1 - \operatorname{erf} \left(\frac{W \cdot (t - t_0) - L}{\sqrt{4 \cdot D_L \cdot (t - t_0)}} \right) \right] + \exp \left(\frac{W \cdot L}{D_L} \right) \cdot \left[\operatorname{erf} \left(\frac{W \cdot (t - t_0) - L}{\sqrt{4 \cdot D_L \cdot (t - t_0)}} \right) - 1 \right] \right\}.$$

2.3 Example data

First, pure CO_2 and N_2 gas were measured as a baseline. Example measurement waveforms and corresponding curve fits are illustrated in Figure 2 for CO_2 gas. Resulting swarm parameters such as the bulk drift velocity W , and the effective ionization rate R_{net} , are shown in Figure 3.

Currently, different binary mixtures of CO_2/N_2 are being investigated, and example experimental waveforms and results are shown in Figure 4.

Figure 2: Example waveforms and curve fits for CO_2 at 7.5 Td, 70 Td, 100 Td, and 1000 Td.

Figure 3: Example results for CO₂ at different pressures.

Figure 4: Example waveforms and results for a binary mixture of N₂ and CO₂ at different pressures.

2.4 Data access

The data gathered can be accessed publicly and freely via the ETHZ-database on the LXCat project website (www.lxcat.net/ETHZ). Task 2.1 runs in total over 24 months and new data will continuously be uploaded to the database until the task is completed.

The evaluation tools and methods are implemented in Python and made publicly available over GitLab at the following URL: https://gitlab.com/ethz_hvl/APTX.

3 STATUS OF 1D MODEL FOR BREAKDOWN PREDICTION

Part of Task 2.2 is to develop a 1D-model for $N_2/O_2/CO_2$ mixtures up to 15 bar to predict discharge inception, streamer development, streamer-to-leader transition, leader propagation and breakdown probability for arbitrary geometries and all voltage waveshapes. This model is under development and the present status of the model is published as part of D2.1. The model is based on the work of [3] and uses a novel set of thermodynamic data that was calculated based on the assumption of thermodynamic equilibrium of the chemical reactions at the given temperature and pressure.

Task 2.2 runs in total over 48 months and the model is continuously updated and continuously made available via the same platform. Extensions include a kinetic reaction model with a complete set of chemical decomposition and recombination reaction pathways.

Figure 5: Schematic of Python implementation of the 1D leader model.

3.1 Model description

A schematic overview of the python implementation can be seen in Figure 5. Four main classes are implemented, representing a gas or gas mixture, a protrusion geometry, a stepped leader propagation with its parameters and finally a breakdown class that helps contain and modify the parameters of the stepped leader model. A module called *physical equations* is implemented as well. It contains methods to compute properties during stepped leader propagation, e.g., thermal dissociation rates and time lags. The methods of the step computation and breakdown prediction class are then able to compute the characteristic breakdown fields amongst other quantities. The plotting module contains scripts to plot various results/parameters of interest to the user [4]. The reader is referred to the code documentation for a detailed description of each of these modules.

3.2 Model outputs

The model computes the following quantities based on the gas mixture properties:

- t_e : The statistical time lag, i.e., the time to first electron for positive and negative polarities.
- x_{inc} : The streamer inception voltage using the streamer criterion.
- x_{min} : The minimum field strength for leader breakdown.
- x_{max} : The field strength for immediate leader breakdown, i.e., with no formative time lag.

These four properties makes it possible to estimate the breakdown strength for arbitrary voltage waveforms and electrode configurations. An example for SF₆ is provided in Figure 6.

These quantities can be experimentally validated for a given geometry using the statistical time lag experiment at ETH. In addition to these quantities, it is also possible to investigate the leader channel lengths, temperatures and propagation times for each leader step in the discharge process shown in Figure 7. Currently, experimental validation of these quantities is not possible.

3.3 Current status

The implementation is validated with published results for SF₆ [3]. In addition, swarm parameters and thermodynamic input files for CO₂/O₂ based mixtures are provided in the latest release. Validation examples for CO₂/O₂ mixtures will be added in the future. The main challenge with extending this model for atmospheric gas mixtures lies in the fact that the field strength of a propagating streamer for these gases is typically lower than the critical field strength, which is a fundamental assumption in the model.

3.4 Software access

The model is implemented in Python and made publicly available over GitLab at the following URL: https://gitlab.com/ethz_hvl/step.

Figure 6: Breakdown field for AC/DC and LI voltage applications in SF₆ for a protrusion on one electrode side and TR100 (plane electrode with 100 micron equivalent roughness on the other electrode side). The highlighted yellow curves indicate the breakdown fields for each electrode configuration for a given voltage waveform. The total breakdown curve indicates the polarity independent breakdown voltage when both electrodes are present. The “breakdown both sides” curve indicates the polarity dependent breakdown curve when both electrodes are present.

Figure 7: Development of the leader channel and its quantities. The considered electrode configuration included a protrusion of length 1 mm, radius 250 microns, and a gap distance of 20 mm with positive polarity on the protrusion side. As gas insulation, SF₆ was modeled at 2 bar pressure. The applied normalized background field was 0.5 and the inception mechanism was chosen to be the *stem* mechanism.

4 STATUS OF 3D MODEL FOR PD AND STREAMER SIMULATIONS

The 3D computer model for partial discharge (PD) and streamer discharges are provided as extensions to the chombo-discharge code [5]. The base code is implemented using both fluid and particle solvers, and uses an embedded boundary (EB) formalism on adaptive Cartesian grids, i.e., with *adaptive mesh refinement* (AMR). The code is implemented entirely in C++, and parallelized with the message passing interface (MPI). Scaling to tens of thousands of CPU cores have been demonstrated for other applications [6]. Note that chombo-discharge has a rich set of features consisting of various physics models for predicting gas discharge behavior at different levels of detail. As the software is rather extensive, a full discussion is not included here and the reader is instead directed to the chombo-discharge code documentation, see <https://chombo-discharge.github.io/chombo-discharge/>.

Extensions to chombo-discharge due to D2.1 are:

- Implementation of a low-fidelity quantitative prediction model for Townsend discharges in any geometry. The formulation takes place as a generalized Paschen curve, implemented using a volumetric formalism analogous to the volumetric streamer criterion in [7].
- Implementation of cathode-feedback for plasma fluid and particle models, in order to provide a high-fidelity description of Townsend avalanches in small gaps/voids, as well as Trichel pulses and other PD-related phenomena. An example computer simulation that shows a PD event in an air-filled cavity is shown in Figure 8.

A separate submission to a peer-reviewed journal that discusses these aspects is in preparation and will be submitted in early 2025. This submission is not a part of D2.1 and is therefore not discussed further in this report.

The PD simulation features in the new models are entirely based on an expansion of previous streamer-based models. In particular, the prediction of the PD inception voltage (PDIV) due to Townsend avalanches is based on a generalized Paschen curve, formulated volumetrically and thus valid for general geometries. For the high-fidelity PD simulation features, secondary emission due to ion and photon bombardment was added to a particle-based streamer simulation model [8], which enables the self-consistent simulation of PD events where Townsend avalanches are the initiating mechanism.

4.1 Accessing the new models

For D2.1, the new model for PD descriptions is released as extensions of the following physics models in chombo-discharge: *DischargeInception*, and *ItoKMC*. Relative to the chombo-discharge root directory, these models are located in the subfolders:

- Physics/DischargeInception (for low-fidelity parametric modeling).
- Physics/ItoKMC (for high-fidelity particle modeling).

Both models are extensively documented via the chombo-discharge code documentation, see:

- <https://chombo-discharge.github.io/chombo-discharge/Applications/DischargeInceptionModel.html>

- <https://chombo-discharge.github.io/chombo-discharge/Applications/ItoKMC.html>

Figure 8: Example computer simulation of the initial phase of a partial discharge event inside a gas-filled cavity in a solid insulator. The particles show the residual positive ions after electron avalanches. These ions drift toward the cathode-side of the void where they cause secondary electron emission, which drives the discharge. The left column shows a discharge with a high-emissive void surface ($\gamma = 10^{-3}$), and the right column shows the evolution with a low-emissive void surface ($\gamma = 10^{-5}$).

4.2 Software access

chombo-discharge can be accessed from:

- <https://github.com/chombo-discharge/chombo-discharge>, or alternatively
- <https://zenodo.org/records/14275524>

chombo-discharge is licensed under GPL-3.0, and is thus open-source and freely accessible at either zenodo or github. New versions of chombo-discharge are released monthly, and releases are indexed as v.<year>.<month>. For example, the final release of 2024 is indexed as v24.12. Usage of chombo-discharge is free of charge.

4.3 Software installation and usage

chombo-discharge has numerous compilation options that are too extensive to be discussed here. The user is referred to the installation instructions in the chombo-discharge documentation found at <https://chombo-discharge.github.io/chombo-discharge/Base/Installation.html>.

Note that chombo-discharge is furthermore targeted at both consumer and professional hardware, as it runs on both desktops as well as some of the worlds largest supercomputers.

4.4 Examples

Example files that run these codes are included in the

- Exec/Examples/DischargeInception/PartialDischarge
- Exec/Examples/ItoKMC/PartialDischarge

Note that these paths are relative to the chombo-discharge installation location. These two examples use the new features of the chombo-discharge codes for solving for the partial discharge inception voltage (PDIV) and PD evolution using both the low-fidelity and high-fidelity descriptions.

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